

Enabling Sparse Attention via ReLU

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Abstract: A learned sparsity based attention would not let model focus on specific tokens and could potentially lead to better generalization, related work introduced changes in attention matrix and its mask’s structure to allow sparse attention but potentially while limiting expressiveness via strict structures. We propose a solution which model can know which tokens to mask for softmax along with causal mask, successfully completely ignoring specific tokens without hurting expressiveness and achieving better generalization by getting a lower validation loss on same scale.

Code is available at <https://github.com/notlober/reluattn>

1 Introduction

The success of large language models can be largely attributed to the self attention mechanism. Self attention uses a matrix of token to token interactions and assigns score to each interaction then normalizes them via Softmax function. In recent research, like Sparse Transformer, utilized sparse factorizations of the attention matrix to enable sparsity in attention and reduce time/memory to $O(N\sqrt{N})$. In this research, we introduce a new way to enable sparsity in attention scores in token by token interaction matrix via learned activations and using ReLU activation function.

2 Method

We begin with the standard self-attention formulation, specifically for a causal-masked and single-headed version frequently used in autoregressive large language models, then add attention scores ReLU activation function before masking:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\text{ReLU} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) + m_c \right) V, \quad (1)$$

where $m_c \in \{-\infty, 0\}$ is the causal mask that enables softmax to ignore certain positions by setting them to $-\infty$. With addition of ReLU negative values become 0 too and masked along with causal part, so this successfully enables learned sparsity via ReLU, allowing only and only positive scores to contribute to the final attention distribution.

3 Experiments

As experiments, we included the standard softmax attention and our relu including attention mechanism on training and validation loss on shakespeare-char dataset, specifically the one used in nanoGPT repository (<https://github.com/karpathy/nanoGPT>). the results are shown below:

Step	+ReLU Train Loss	+ReLU Val Loss	Softmax Train Loss	Softmax Val Loss
500	1.5605	1.7567	1.5273	1.7352
1500	1.1644	1.4636	1.1485	1.4655
3000	0.8868	1.5101	0.8618	1.5259
3500	0.8081	1.5601	0.7769	1.5918
4000	0.7382	1.6013	0.7052	1.6340
5000	0.6505	1.6384	0.6203	1.6689

Table 1: Comparison of training and validation loss for standard softmax and relu along with softmax attention mechanisms at various steps.

The results show that train loss gets a little worse but validation loss gets a little better, potentially meaning of better generalization due to regularization comes from sparsity.

4 Conclusion

We have proposed a way to enable learned sparse attention without hurting accuracy of model too much and achieving better validation loss on same scale. We started within the standard causal self attention formulation which provides a good baseline, but potentially limited expressiveness since softmax considers all tokens without ability to completely "dropping" any token, to solve this we introduced ReLU activation before masking and softmax to baseline formulation and successfully achieved lower validation loss, and we believe this is similar to some kind of regularization.

References

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